

E- ISSN: 2980-4760
P- ISSN: 2980-4752

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8325786

Emotional Intelligence of Faculty among Public Higher Education Institutions (HEI's)

Adawia Jamasali

adawiaj@gmail.com

Instructor, School of Arts and Sciences
Sulu State College
Jolo, Sulu, Philippines

 International Journal of Multidisciplinary Educational Research and Innovation is an international peer-reviewed academic journal that highly values the importance of developing knowledge in the field of multidisciplinary educational and innovative research. The journal's scope is broad, with the goals of disseminating information and providing a place for discussion, theoretical inquiry, practical applications, research discoveries, and experimentations in the field of education.

Recommended Citation

Jamasali, A. (2023). Emotional Intelligence of Faculty among Public Higher Education Institutions (HEI's). *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Educational Research and Innovation*. 1(3), 89-108. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8325786>.

Authors retain copyright. Articles published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC-BY) International License. This license allows this work to be copied, distributed, remixed, transformed, and built upon for any purpose provided that appropriate attribution is given, a link is provided to the license, and changes made were indicated.

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF FACULTY AMONG PUBLIC HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS (HEI'S)

Adawia Jamasali¹

¹Instructor, School of Arts and Sciences, Sulu State College, Jolo, Sulu, Philippines

ABSTRACT

This descriptive-correlational study determines the emotional intelligence of faculty of public higher education institutions (HEIs) in Sulu during the academic year 2021–2022. The study adapted a purposeful sampling method in which there were two hundred samples. The data were analyzed using the weighted mean, standard deviation, t-test for independent samples, one-way ANOVA, and Pearson's r. The following findings are drawn from this study: 1) The majority of the respondents are female, between the ages of 32 and 40, married, with 10 years or fewer of experience teaching, permanent status, and a master's degree with some coursework toward a doctorate. 2) Teachers who participated in the survey agreed that Sulu's faculty members have higher levels of emotional intelligence than the national average. Thus, these educators possess a strong capacity to apply knowledge to various situations, specifically in relation to social, personal, emotional, and cognitive abilities that determine how someone responds to various clamor and tensions. On average, there is no significant difference in the extent of emotional intelligence among faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are categorized according to gender, civil status, length of service, and educational attainment. However, there are substantial age and employment status disparities, with teacher responders who are 51 years of age or older and who are employed on a temporary basis having greater abilities to gauge the level of emotional intelligence.

Keywords: *Emotional Intelligence, Higher Education Institutions, Writing Proficiency*

Received: May 2023
Revised: June 2023
Accepted: July 2023
Available: August 2023

INTRODUCTION

In today's world, survival is the common human pursuit in life. That is, a quest for a successful life that is tied to freedom from emotional and mental strife is one's paramount dream.

A higher education institution is a typical prototype of a social community. This is where different groups of people with varied social orientations are pooled together. Consequently, social interaction processes are inevitably influenced by individuals social traits and characters. It is wise to speculate that members of such a social community, in this case the faculty, are expected to adequately deal with affective information (Mayer, Caruso, & Salovey, 2016).

Since emotional health is equally important as mental and physical health, for faculty members to protect and promote their emotional health and well-being, they ought to apply social, personal, and emotional skills and abilities that affect how they cope with different clamors and tensions (Dollard, 2018).

After all, emotional well-being in general and emotional intelligence influence how people identify the capacity of a person to live a good life and impact their psychological health (Poonamallee et al.). In

Authors retain copyright. Articles published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC-BY) International License. This license allows this work to be copied, distributed, remixed, transformed, and built upon for any purpose provided that appropriate attribution is given, a link is provided to the license, and changes made were indicated.

other words, faculty members of higher education institutions who belong to different academic fields are not only intelligent but also resilient and optimistic. For them to succeed in their teaching careers, it takes more than just mental abilities to demonstrate emotional intelligence (Patti et al., 2018).

So, to adequately deal with affective information, faculty members need to have emotional intelligence, as nurtured by emotional traits and abilities (Daloos, 2015; and Lopes, 2016).

While research on teachers' emotional intelligence is seemingly adequate in some western countries, study in this field is rarely done in the Philippines, especially in the context of higher education institutions. Therefore, this study was conducted to bridge the knowledge gap that is perceived as critical in the field of educational administration.

Research Questions

1. What is the population makeup of instructors in Sulu's public HEIs by:
 - 1.1 Gender
 - 1.2 Age
 - 1.3 Civil status
 - 1.4 Length of service
 - 1.5 Status of employment
 - 1.6 Educational attainment?

2. What is the extent of emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu in the context of:
 - 2.1 Perception of emotions
 - 2.2 Managing own emotions
 - 2.3 Managing other's emotions, and
 - 2.4 Utilization of emotions?

3. Is there a significant difference in the emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu in the context when data are grouped categorized according to:
 - 4.1 Gender
 - 4.2 Age
 - 4.3 Civil status
 - 4.4 Length of service
 - 4.5 Status of employment, and
 - 4.6 Educational attainment?

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

On Emotional Intelligence

According to Moon, Jayet's study from 2021 titled "Effect of Emotional Intelligence and Leadership Styles on Risk Intelligent Decision Making and Risk Management," there is a lot of uncertainty in the world today. As a result, managers have a responsibility to make judgments based on objective factors when addressing organizational risks. Risk judgments frequently involve several assumptions and biases, which results in bad choices.

However, there is no empirical data that explains the relationship between emotional intelligence (EI), leadership styles, and managers' perceptions of risk. Leaders who utilize emotional intelligence (EI)

Authors retain copyright. Articles published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC-BY) International License. This license allows this work to be copied, distributed, remixed, transformed, and built upon for any purpose provided that appropriate attribution is given, a link is provided to the license, and changes made were indicated.

abilities are better positioned to question internal biases and preconceptions to enhance decision-making.

This research's objective was to examine the applicability of the notion of emotional intelligence to risk-based decision-making while contrasting various leadership philosophies. The study used data from a questionnaire survey completed by 173 working people. Using the t statistic and, where appropriate, Chi-square testing, the study hypotheses examined the mediating roles of emotional intelligence (EI) and leadership philosophies in risk perceptions. The analysis's findings supported the idea that EI plays a crucial role in preventing harmful internal biases from entering the decision-making process. However, transformational leaders are less prejudiced and more emotionally intelligent. Compared to transactional leaders, these characteristics enable the development of a proper risk mindset and improve risk-intelligent judgments.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A comparative-correlational study, a research methodology was used in this study, that is, in order to characterize, measure, and infer, in addition to finding relationships between variables and to permit using current information to forecast future occurrences college faculty's expertise or phenomena both teaching and non-teaching workers, namely: 1) The sociodemographic makeup of HEI professors in Sulu with regards to age, civil status, length of service, and gender employment and educational status achievability; 2) The degree of emotional perception of intelligence in the context Emotions, self-management of emotions Utilizing others' emotions and feelings of Emotions; 3) The stark contrast between the emotional intelligence level when information is categorized based on civil status, gender, age, term of service, employment status, and academic achievement; faculty members the majority of public HEIs in Sulu were information that was quantified to address the study's research questions. Internet and library searches, and information was gathered from publications. These were added to strengthen the study's theoretical and conceptual underpinnings. Information on the respondents was acquired via survey questions.

Research Respondents

Regardless of their academic levels or positions, the population and sample of this study consisted of faculty members of public HEIs in Sulu who were working and teaching at various colleges and universities throughout the academic year 2021–2022.

Target sample distribution within Sulu's public HEI faculty

Public Higher Education Institutions In Sulu	Faculty
MSU-Sulu	80
Sulu State College	83
HBSAT	25
Lapak Agricultural College	12
Total	200

Authors retain copyright. Articles published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC-BY) International License. This license allows this work to be copied, distributed, remixed, transformed, and built upon for any purpose provided that appropriate attribution is given, a link is provided to the license, and changes made were indicated.

Research Instrument

A survey questionnaire was the main instrument employed to gather data on the extent of emotional intelligence among faculty at public HEIs in Sulu. The standardized questionnaire of Lucero & Ocampo, Jr. (2019), which was used in their study on emotional IQ and leadership traits by one of the master instructors, served as the basis for the research instrument.

A 5-point Likert-Scale was used to measure the variables subsumed under the emotional intelligence.

Data Analysis

The appropriate statistical procedures were thought to be both descriptive and inferential data analysis. They assisted in managing the data that was gathered for this inquiry.

Specifically:

- 1) For research question #1, percentages and frequency counts were used to determine the respondents' profiles;
- 2) For the second study question, the mean and the standard deviation were used to evaluate your emotional intelligence level.
- 3) T-test for research question no. 3: Independent samples were used to assess the major variations in the degree of emotional intelligence in groups of data based on gender; one-way analysis of ANOVA variance for grouped data according to military history, age, civil status, and educational success;
- 4) The Pearson Product Moment association Coefficient (Pearson's r) was used to calculate the significant association between the subcategories that make up emotional intelligence for research question number four.

The following intervals for rating scales were taken into consideration when analyzing the computed results from both descriptive and

A) Rating scales are inferential statistical instruments. The respondents' perceptions of the interval based on a 5-point Likert scale, emotional intelligence.

Scale: Value Descriptors: Point Scale 5 - 4

Point	Scale Value	Descriptors
5	4.50-5.00	High Average
4	3.50-4.49	Above Average
3	2.50- 3.49	Average
2	1.50- 2.49	Low Average
1	1.00- 1.49	Very Low Average

RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

This study reveals the following findings:

1) For Research Question Number 1: On the Demographic Profile of Teacher Respondents, Out of 200 teacher respondents, the majority are female, between 32 and 40 years old, married, have teaching experience of ten years or less, have permanent status, and have a master's degree with some units in a doctoral program.

2) For Research Question Number 2: On the Extent of Emotional Intelligence

Teacher-respondents affirmed that faculty at public HEIs in Sulu have an above-average rate of emotional intelligence. Thus, these educators possess a strong capacity to apply knowledge to various situations, specifically in relation to social, personal, emotional, and cognitive abilities that determine how someone responds to various clamors and tensions.

3) For Research Question Number 3: On Differences in Emotional Intelligence

When data are grouped based on Sulu duration of service, gender, civil status, and educational performance, there are often no obvious differences in the level of emotion among the professors at public HEIs. However, there are substantial disparities based on age and job status, and teacher responders who are 51 years of age or older and have temporary employment status are better able to gauge the level of emotional intelligence.

1. What is the population makeup of instructors in Sulu's public HEIs by: 1.1 Gender, 1.2 Age, 1.3 Civil status, 1.4 Length of service, 1.5 Status of employment, and 1.6 Educational attainment?

1.1 In terms of Gender

Table 1.1 depicts the racial and ethnic makeup of the gender differences among teachers who responded.

This table makes it evident that 93 (46.5%) out of 200 teacher respondents—or five out of ten—are female. These findings indicate that the majority, or more than half, of the instructor responders are female. This finding suggests that there are somewhat more female faculty members working in Sulu's higher education institutions than there are male faculty members.

Table 1.1 Demographic profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of gender

Gender	Number of Teachers	Percent
Male	93	46.5%
Female	ten7	53.5%
Total	200	ten0%

1.2 In terms of Age

Table 1.2 displays the demographic information for the gender differences among the teachers who responded. This table shows that, of the 200 educators who replied, 55 (27.5%) were 30 or younger, 60 (30.0%) were 31–40 years old, 48 (24.0%) were 41–50 years old, and 37 (18.5%) were 51 years of age or older. Although there is no age discrepancy between teachers and other groups, these statistics indicate that at least one-third of teacher responses are between the ages of 32 and 40. This finding suggests that middle-aged college professors are highly concentrated or available at public HEIs in Sulu.

Table 1.2 Demographic profile of teacher-respondents in terms of age

Age	Number of Teachers	Percent
30 years old & below	55	27.50%
31-40 years old	60	30.0%
41-50 years old	48	24.0%
51 years old & above	37	18.5%
Total	200	ten0%

1.3 In terms of Civil Status

According to their civil status, the respondents who were instructors in higher education institutions in Sulu are described in Table 1.3. Out of 200 educators who answered, it is evident from this table that 71 (5.5%) are single, 99 (49.5%) are married, 17 (8.5%) are separated, and 13 (6.5%) are widowed. This indicates that the majority, or about half, of the teacher responders to this research are married. This finding suggests that instructors who are married and considered to have embraced a variety of

activities, including teaching employment, family commitments, raising children, social obligations, and the like, make up the faculty force of public HEIs in Sulu.

Table 1.3 Demographic profile of teacher-respondent in terms of civil status

Civil Status	Number of Teachers	Percent
Single	71	35.5%
Married	99	49.5%
Separated	17	8.5%
Widowed	13	6.5%
Total	200	ten0%

1.4 In terms of Length of Service

According to their tenure of employment, the demographic profile of the teachers who responded from Sulu's public higher education institutions is shown in Table 1.4. This information suggests that, of the 200 instructors who replied, 98 (49.0%) have ten years or less of experience, 34 (17.0%) have eleven to twenty years, 43 (21.5%) have twenty-one to thirty-five years, and 25 (12.5%) have thirty-one years or more. This result suggests that the majority of the instructors at HEIs in Sulu have regular teaching obligations, however a sizeable number of contractual staff are also recorded. In this survey, this means that roughly half of the teacher respondents had teaching experience of ten years or less.

Table 1.4 Demographics of the responders who were teachers regarding the duration of service length

Length of Service	Number of Teachers	Percent
ten years % below	98	49.0%
11-20 years	34	17.0%
21-30 years	43	21.5%
31 years & above	25	12.5%
Total	200	ten0%

1.5 In terms of Status of Employment

In terms of work status, Table 1.5 displays the demographic profile of the teachers who responded from public higher education institutions in Sulu. This chart clearly demonstrates that, of the 200 educators who replied, 114 (57.3%) are permanent, 40 (20.1%) are temporary, and 45 (22.6%) are contractual or part-time. This indicates that more than half of the teacher respondents in this research had a permanent status.

Although there are also known to be a sizable number of contractual staff, this finding suggests that the majority of instructors at public HEIs in Sulu have regular teaching obligations.

Table 1.5: Demographic profile of the teacher respondents in terms of status of employment

Status of Employment	Number of Teachers	Percent
Permanent	114	57.3%
Temporary	40	20.1%
Contractual/ Part-time	45	22.6%
Total	200	ten0%

1.6 In terms of Educational Attainment

The demographic breakdown of the respondents who worked as instructors at Sulu's public higher education institutions is shown in Table 1.6. Out of 200 educators who responded, the table shows that 33 (16.5%) have a bachelor's degree, 66 (33.0%) have a bachelor's degree plus MA units, 48 (24.0%) have a full master's degree, 33 (16.5%) have a master's degree plus doctoral units, and 20 (ten.0%) have a full doctorate degree. This indicates that more than a third of the teacher responders to this research hold a Master's degree and are enrolled in a PhD program in part. This finding suggests that the majority of public HEI instructors in Sulu possess the necessary academic credentials.

Table 1.6 Demographic profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of educational attainment

Educational Attainment	Number of Teachers	Percent
Bachelor's degree	33	16.5%
Bachelor's degree plus MA units	66	33.0%
Full-fledged master's degree	48	24.0%
Master's degree plus doctoral units	33	16.5%
Full-fledged doctorate degree	20	ten.0%
Total	200	ten0%

2. What is the extent of emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu in the context of: 2.1 Perception of emotions, 2.2 Managing own emotions, 2.3 Managing other's emotions, and 2.4 Utilization of emotions?

2.1 In terms of Perception of Emotion

Table 2.1 shows the extent of emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu in the context of their perception of emotions. In this group, there are teacher-respondents who received a weighted average score of 3.9794 overall with a standard deviation of .42953, which is rated as "above average." This result indicates that teacher-respondents perceive that faculty at public HEIs in Sulu are rated above average in their ability to apply knowledge to different circumstances in life. It is a collection of social, emotional, and personal traits and talents that influence how a person acts and handles various stresses and tensions. Moreover, respondents who work in this category have an above average rating for the following: "I find it difficult to grasp the nonverbal cues others give I am cognizant of the signals others send through non-verbal cues".

Table 2.1 Extent of emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu in the context of perception of emotions

	Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	I find it hard to understand the non-verbal messages of other people.	3.7050	.87854	Above Average
2	I am aware of my emotions as I experience them.	3.9799	.66636	Above Average
3	I am aware of the non-verbal messages I send to others.	4.1350	.78091	Above Average

4	By looking at their facial expressions, I recognize the emotions people are experiencing are experiencing.	4.0600	.72041	Above Average
5	I know why my emotions change.	4.2350	.72968	Above Average
6	I easily recognize my emotions as I experience them.	4.1150	.65ten7	Above Average
7	I am aware of the non-verbal messages other people send.	3.8650	.80624	Above Average
8	I know what other people are feeling just by looking at them.	3.8643	.82675	Above Average
9	I can tell how people are feeling by listening to the tone of their voice.	4.1200	.74050	Above Average
te n	It is difficult for me to understand why people feel the way they do.	3.6800	.89533	Above Average
Total Weighted Mean		3.9794	.42953	Above Average

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=High; (4) 3.50-4.49=Above Average; (3) 2.50- 3.49=Average; (2) 1.50- 2.49=Low Average; (1) 1.00- 1.49=Very Low Average

2.2 In terms of Managing Own Emotion

Table 2.2 shows the extent of emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu in the context of managing their own emotions. In this group, there are teacher respondents who received a weighted average score of 4.0717 with a standard deviation of .48232, which is rated as "above average." This outcome shows that respondents who were teachers believe that Sulu's public HEIs' faculties are regarded as having above-average ability to encourage the power of creation through thought and feelings and be able to justify them. Moreover, under this category, employee-respondents rated above average the following items: "When I am faced with obstacles, I remember times I faced similar obstacles and overcame them, "I expect that I will do well on most things I try, "I expect good things to happen, "When I experience a positive emotion, I know how to make it last, "I seek out activities that make me happy, "I have control over my emotions, and "I motivate myself by imagining a good outcome to tasks I take on".

Table 2.2 Extent of emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu in the context of managing own emotions

	Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	When I am faced with obstacles, I remember times I faced similar obstacles and overcame them.	3.9500	.69996	Above Average
2	I expect that I will do well on most things I try.	4.1200	.78016	Above Average
3	I expect good things to happen.	4.1700	.78369	Above Average
4	When I experience a positive emotion, I know how to make it last.	4.1350	.63939	Above Average
5	I seek out activities that make me happy.	4.2150	.67159	Above Average
6	I have control over my emotions.	4.0400	.65617	Above Average
7	I motivate myself by imagining a good outcome to tasks I take on.	4.2900	.76736	Above Average
8	When I am faced with a challenge, I give up because I believe I will fail.	3.5650	1.1144	Above Average
9	I use good moods to help myself keep trying in the face of obstacles.	4.1600	.80476	Above Average

Authors retain copyright. Articles published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC-BY) International License. This license allows this work to be copied, distributed, remixed, transformed, and built upon for any purpose provided that appropriate attribution is given, a link is provided to the license, and changes made were indicated.

Total Weighted Mean	4.0717	.48232	Above Average
----------------------------	---------------	---------------	----------------------

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=High; (4) 3.50-4.49=Above Average; (3) 2.50- 3.49=Average; (2) 1.50- 2.49=Low Average; (1) 1.00- 1.49=Very Low Average

2.3 In terms of Managing Other's Emotion

Table 2.3 shows the extent of emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu in the context of managing others emotions. Under this category, teacher-respondents obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.0404 with a standard deviation of .46495, which is rated as "above average." This outcome shows that respondents who were teachers believe that Sulu's public HEIs' faculties are regarded as having above-average ability to control one's emotions as a skill that aids the individual in managing their own as well as others.

Moreover, under this category, employee-respondents rated above average the following items: "I know when to speak about my personal problems to others, "Other people find it easy to confide in me, "I like to share my emotions with others, "I arrange events others enjoy, "I present myself in a way that makes a good impression on others, "I compliment others when they have done something well, "When another person tells me about an important event in his or her life, and "I almost feel as though I have experienced this event myself".

Table 2.3 Extent of emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu in the context of managing other's emotions

	Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	I know when to speak about my personal problems to others.	4.1950	.72775	Above Average
2	Other people find it easy to confide in me.	3.8900	.80694	Above Average
3	I like to share my emotions with others.	3.6250	.96906	Above Average
4	I arrange events others enjoy.	3.9200	.77239	Above Average
5	I present myself in a way that makes a good impression on others.	4.0950	.74076	Above Average
6	I compliment others when they have done something well.	4.2400	.72459	Above Average
7	When another person tells me about an important event in his or her life, I almost feel as though I have experienced this event myself.	4.1450	.66799	Above Average
8	I help other people feel better when they are down.	4.2161	.74437	Above Average
	Total Weighted Mean	4.0404	.46495	Above Average

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=High; (4) 3.50-4.49=Above Average; (3) 2.50- 3.49=Average; (2) 1.50- 2.49=Low Average; (1) 1.00- 1.49=Very Low Average

2.4 In terms of utilization of Emotion

Table 2.4 shows the extent of emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu in the context of emotional utilization. In this group, there are teacher-respondents with a weighted average score overall of 4.1932 with a standard deviation of .54882, which is rated as "above average" as well as in others. This outcome shows that respondents who were teachers believe that Sulu's public HEIs' faculties are regarded as having above-average ability to know the ability to feel emotions, comprehend the complexities of emotions in nature and the feelings they evoke, and how they transition from one phase to the next.

Moreover, under this category, employee-respondents rated above average the following items: "Some of the major events of my life have led me to re-evaluate what is important and not important, "When

Authors retain copyright. Articles published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC-BY) International License. This license allows this work to be copied, distributed, remixed, transformed, and built upon for any purpose provided that appropriate attribution is given, a link is provided to the license, and changes made were indicated.

my mood changes, I see new possibilities, "Emotions are one of the things that make my life worth living, "When I am in a positive mood, solving problems is easy for me, "When I am in a positive mood, I am able to come up with new ideas, and "When I feel a change in emotions, I tend to come up with new ideas".

Table 2.3 Extent of emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu in the context of managing other’s emotions

	Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	Some of the major events of my life have led me to re-evaluate what is important and not important.	4.1400	.71622	Above Average
2	When my mood changes, I see new possibilities.	4.0500	.71418	Above Average
3	Emotions are one of the things that make my life worth living.	4.2350	.67234	Above Average
4	When I am in a positive mood, solving problems is easy for me.	4.2800	.71706	Above Average
5	When I am in a positive mood, I am able to come up with new ideas.	4.2814	.77928	Above Average
6	When I feel a change in emotions, I tend to come up with new ideas.	4.1759	.71366	Above Average
Total Weighted Mean		4.1932	.54882	Above Average

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=High; (4) 3.50-4.49=Above Average; (3) 2.50- 3.49=Average; (2) 1.50- 2.49=Low Average; (1) 1.00- 1.49=Very Low Average

3. Is there a significant difference in the emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu in the context when data are grouped categorized according to: 4.1 Gender, 4.2 Age, 4.3 Civil status, 4.4 Length of service, 4.5 Status of employment, and 4.6 Educational attainment?

3.1 According to Gender

Table 3.1 shows the difference in the emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu when data are categorized according to gender. From this table, it can be seen that the mean t-values, probability values, and differences between all categories that fall within the scope of emotional intelligence are not alpha.05. This means that, generally, male and female teacher respondents in this study do not differ in their perceptions of the extent of emotional intelligence. This result implies that being a male teacher-respondent may not make him a better perceiver of the extent of emotional intelligence than his female counterparts, or vice versa.

Moreover, it can be inferred further that teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu, though they vary in gender, do not differ in ways of perceiving emotional intelligence. That is, teachers of HEIs in Sulu perceived in similar ways how individual faculty apply knowledge to different circumstances in life. They don't disagree when evaluating a group of interpersonal, emotional, and social skills that impact a person's ability to cope with various clamors and tensions.

In light of this, it is acceptable to claim that changeable gender has no noteworthy impact on how things are done by educators working in public higher education and how they perceive the depth of emotional distress in Sulu.

Therefore, the hypothesis that states that "there is no significant difference in the emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu in the context when data are grouped and categorized according to gender" is accepted.

Table 3.1 Differences in the emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped categorized according to gender

VARIABLES		Mean	S. D.	Mean Difference	t	Sig.	Description
Grouping							
Perception of emotions	Male	3.969	.4080	-.01775	-.291	.771	Not Significant
	Female	3.987	.4491				
Managing own emotions	Male	4.081	.4281	.01790	.261	.794	Not Significant
	Female	4.063	.5267				
Managing other's	Male	4.045	.4624	.009ten	.138	.891	Not Significant
	Female	4.036	.4692				
Utilization of emotions	Male	4.190	.5547	-.00599	-.077	.939	Not Significant
	Female	4.196	.5462				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

3.2 According to Age

Table 3.2 shows the difference in the emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu when data are categorized according to age. This table shows that, with the exception of "Managing Own Emotion" and "Utilization of Emotion," all other sub-categories included under the heading "Emotional Intelligence" have F-values and probability values that are significant at alpha.05. This means that, generally, given the fact that teacher-respondents vary in age range, in this study they indeed differ in their perceptions toward the extent of emotional intelligence. This result implies that being a teacher-respondent whose age range is within 51 years and above may probably make him/her a better perceiver of the extent of emotional intelligence than other teacher-respondents whose age range is within 30 years and below, 31 to 40 years old, and 41 to 50 years old, or vice versa.

Moreover, it can be inferred further that teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu vary in age range, yet they indeed differ in ways of perceiving emotional intelligence. That is, teachers of HEIs in Sulu perceived in different ways how individual faculty applied knowledge to different circumstances in life. They don't disagree when evaluating a group of interpersonal, emotional, and social skills that impact a person's ability to cope with various clamors and tensions.

Consequently, it is acceptable to claim that fluctuating age has a tremendous impact on how things are done by educators working in public higher education and how they perceive the depth of emotional distress in Sulu. Therefore, the hypothesis that states that "there is no significant difference in the emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu in the context when data are grouped and categorized according to age" is rejected.

IJMERI

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY
EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH AND INNOVATION

Authors retain copyright. Articles published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC-BY) International License. This license allows this work to be copied, distributed, remixed, transformed, and built upon for any purpose provided that appropriate attribution is given, a link is provided to the license, and changes made were indicated.

Table 3.2 Differences in the emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped categorized according to age

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Perception of emotions	Between	3.100	3	1.033	6.026*	.00	Significant
	Within Groups	33.614	19	.171			
	Total	36.714	19				
Managing own emotions	Between	1.552	3	.517	2.266	.08	Not Significant
	Within Groups	44.742	19	.228			
	Total	46.294	19				
Managing other's emotions	Between	2.316	3	.772	3.717*	.01	Significant
	Within Groups	40.705	19	.208			
	Total	43.020	19				
Utilization of emotions	Between	2.235	3	.745	2.531	.05	Not Significant
	Within Groups	57.703	19	.294			
	Total						

*Significant at alpha 0.05

A post-hoc analysis using Scheffe's test was conducted to determine which groups classified according to age have different levels of mean in areas subsumed under the extent of emotional intelligence among faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are categorized according to their demographic profile in terms of age.

The result of the analysis, which is shown in Table 4.3.1, indicates that the difference in the means of the perception of emotion and managing others emotions is obtained by way of lower group means minus higher group means.

On Perception Emotion: It shows that the 51-year-old and above group of respondents obtained a mean difference of .35890* with a standard error of .09060 and a p-value of .002, which is significant at alpha = .05 over the 41–50-year-old group. So under this sub-category, no other group of teacher-respondents is supposed to have better ways of perceiving the extent of emotional intelligence in terms of perception of emotion than teacher-respondents whose age range is within 51 years and above.

On Managing Other's Emotion: It reveals that the group of respondents aged 18 and over acquired an average discrepancy of .32735* with a standard error of .09970 and a p-value of .015, which is significant at alpha = .05 over the 41–50-year-old group. Consequently, no additional groups of teachers are expected to provide better feedback methods for determining the depth of emotional intellect in terms of emotional awareness than the age range of teacher respondents between 51 and older.

Table 3.3.1 Post Hoc Analysis: Differences in the levels of mean in areas subsumed under the extent of emotional intelligence when data are categorized according to their demographic profile in terms of age

Dependent Variables	(I) Grouping by Age	(J) Grouping by Age	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Perception of emotion	51 years old & above	30 years old & below	.25922*	.08805	.037
		31-40 years old	.30973*	.08656	.006
		41-50 years old	.35890*	.09060	.002
	51 years old & above	30 years old & below	.23136	.09690	.131

Authors retain copyright. Articles published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC-BY) International License. This license allows this work to be copied, distributed, remixed, transformed, and built upon for any purpose provided that appropriate attribution is given, a link is provided to the license, and changes made were indicated.

Managing	31-40 years old	.21329	.09526	.175
Other's	41-50 years old	.32735*	.09970	.015
Emotion				

* The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

3.3 According to Civil Status

Table 3.3 shows the difference in the emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu when data are categorized according to civil status. It can be gleaned from this table that the F-values and probability-values of other sub-categories subsumed under the extent of emotional intelligence are not significant at alpha.05. This means that, generally, although teacher-respondents vary in marital status, in this study they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of emotional intelligence. This result implies that a teacher-respondent who is married may not be a better perceiver of the extent of emotional intelligence than other teacher-respondents who are single, separated, and widowed, or vice versa.

Moreover, it can be inferred further that teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu, although they vary in civil status, do not differ in ways of perceiving emotional intelligence. That is, teachers of HEIs in Sulu perceived in similar ways how individual faculty apply knowledge to different circumstances in life. They do not differ in assessing a group of social, personal, and emotional skills and abilities that affect how a person copes with different clamors and tensions.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable civil status has no significant influence on the ways in which teachers of public higher education institutions in Sulu perceive the extent of emotional intelligence. Therefore, the hypothesis that states that "there is no significant difference in the emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu in the context when data are grouped and categorized according to civil status" is accepted. Table 3.3 Differences in the emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped categorized according to civil status

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Perception of emotions	Between	.590	3	.197	1.068	.36	Not Significant
	Within Groups	36.124	19	.184			
	Total	36.714	19				
Managing own emotions	Between	1.075	3	.358	1.553	.20	Not Significant
	Within Groups	45.219	19	.231			
	Total	46.294	19				
Managing other's emotions	Between	.111	3	.037	.169	.91	Not Significant
	Within Groups	42.909	19	.219			
	Total	43.020	19				
Utilization of emotions	Between	.863	3	.288	.955	.41	Not Significant
	Within Groups	59.075	19	.301			
	Total	59.938	19				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

3.4 According to Length of Service

Table 3.4 shows the difference in the emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu when data are categorized according to length of service. It can be gleaned from this table that, except for "Perception of Emotion," the F-values and probability-values of all other sub-categories subsumed under the extent of emotional intelligence are not significant at alpha.05. This means that, generally, although

Authors retain copyright. Articles published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC-BY) International License. This license allows this work to be copied, distributed, remixed, transformed, and built upon for any purpose provided that appropriate attribution is given, a link is provided to the license, and changes made were indicated.

teacher-respondents vary in length of service, in this study they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of emotional intelligence. This result implies that a teacher-respondent who has been in teaching for 31 years and above may not probably be a better perceiver of the extent of emotional intelligence than other teacher-respondents who have had a length of service of 11–20 years and 21–30 years, or vice versa.

Moreover, it can be inferred further that teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu, although they vary in civil status, do not differ in ways of perceiving emotional intelligence. That is, teachers of HEIs in Sulu perceived in similar ways how individual faculty apply knowledge to different circumstances in life. They do not differ in assessing a group of social, personal, and emotional skills and abilities that affect how a person copes with different clamors and tensions.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable length of service has no significant influence on the ways in which teachers of public higher education institutions in Sulu perceive the extent of emotional intelligence. Therefore, the hypothesis that states that "there is no significant difference in the emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu in the context when data are grouped and categorized according to length of service" is accepted.

Table 3.4 Differences in the emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped categorized according to length of service

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig	Description
Perception of emotions	Between	2.348	3	.783	4.464*	.00	Significant
	Within Groups	34.366	19	.175			
	Total	36.714	19				
Managing own emotions	Between	.565	3	.188	.807	.49	Not Significant
	Within Groups	45.729	19	.233			
	Total	46.294	19				
Managing other's emotions	Between	.124	3	.041	.189	.90	Not Significant
	Within Groups	42.896	19	.219			
	Total	43.020	19				
Utilization of emotions	Between	1.404	3	.468	1.567	.19	Not Significant
	Within Groups	58.534	19	.299			
	Total	59.938	19				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

3.5 According to Status of Employment

Table 3.5 shows the difference in the emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu when data are categorized according to status of employment. It can be gleaned from this table that, except for "perception of emotion" and "utilization of emotion, the F-values and probability-values of all other sub-categories subsumed under the extent of emotional intelligence are indeed significant at alpha.05. This means that, despite the fact that teacher-respondents vary in status of employment, in this study they indeed differ in their perceptions toward the extent of emotional intelligence. This result implies that a teacher-respondent who has permanent teaching status may probably have a better perception of the extent of emotional intelligence than other teacher-respondents who have temporary, contractual, or part-time teaching jobs, or vice versa.

Moreover, it can be inferred further that teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu, although they vary in employment status, indeed differ in ways of perceiving emotional intelligence. That is, teachers of HEIs in Sulu perceived differently how individual faculty applied knowledge to different circumstances

Authors retain copyright. Articles published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC-BY) International License. This license allows this work to be copied, distributed, remixed, transformed, and built upon for any purpose provided that appropriate attribution is given, a link is provided to the license, and changes made were indicated.

in life. They do not differ in assessing a group of social, personal, and emotional skills and abilities that affect how a person copes with different clamors and tensions.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable employment status has indeed had a significant influence on the ways in which teachers of public higher education institutions in Sulu perceive the extent of emotional intelligence. Therefore, the hypothesis that states that "there is no significant difference in the emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu in the context when data are grouped and categorized according to employment status" is rejected.

Table 3.5 Differences in the emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped categorized according to status of employment

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig	Description
Perception of emotions	Between	2.257	2	1.128	6.420*	.00	Significant
	Within Groups	34.443	19	.176			
	Total	36.700	19				
Managing own emotions	Between	1.292	2	.646	2.847	.06	Not Significant
	Within Groups	44.454	19	.227			
	Total	45.746	19				
Managing other's emotions	Between	1.586	2	.793	3.758*	.02	Significant
	Within Groups	41.350	19	.211			
	Total	42.935	19				
Utilization of emotions	Between	.090	2	.045	.147	.86	Not Significant
	Within Groups	59.848	19	.305			
	Total	59.938	19				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

A post-hoc analysis using Scheffe's test was conducted to determine which groups classified according to employment status have different levels of mean in areas subsumed under the extent of emotional intelligence among faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are categorized according to their demographic profile in terms of employment status.

The result of the analysis, which is shown in Table 4.5.1, indicates that the difference in the means of the perception of emotion and managing others emotions is obtained by way of lower group means minus higher group means.

On Perception Emotion: It shows that the temporary group of respondents obtained a mean difference of.32306* with a standard error of.091 and a p-value of.002, which is significant at alpha =.05 over the contractual or part-time group. So under this sub-category, no other group of teacher-respondents is supposed to have better ways of perceiving the extent of emotional intelligence in terms of perception of emotion than teacher-respondents whose employment status is temporary.

On Managing Other's Emotion: It shows that the temporary group of respondents obtained a mean difference of.27098* with a standard error of.09981 and a p-value of.027, which is significant at alpha =.05 over the contractual or part-time group. So under this sub-category, no other group of teacher-respondents is supposed to have better ways of perceiving the extent of emotional intelligence in terms of managing others emotions than teacher-respondents whose employment status is temporary.

Table 3.5.1 Post Hoc Analysis: Differences in the levels of mean in areas subsumed under the extent of emotional intelligence among faculty of public HEIs in Sulu when data are categorized according to their demographic profile in terms of employment status

Dependent Variables	(I) Grouping by Employment Status	(J) Grouping by Employment Status	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Perception of emotion	temporary	permanent	.20191*	.07704	.034
		Contractual/ Part-time	.32306*	.0911ten	.002
Managing Other's Emotion	temporary	permanent	.11835	.08441	.376
		Contractual/ Part-time	.27098*	.09981	.027

* The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

3.6 According to Educational Attainment

Table 3.6 shows the difference in the emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu when data are categorized according to educational attainment. It can be gleaned from this table that the F-values and probability-values of all sub-categories subsumed under the extent of emotional intelligence are not significant at alpha.05. This means that, although teacher-respondents vary in educational attainment, in this study they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of emotional intelligence. This result implies that a teacher-respondent who has a doctorate degree may not be a better perceiver of the extent of emotional intelligence than other teacher-respondents who have a bachelor's degree, a bachelor's degree with MA units, a master's degree with doctoral units, or vice versa.

Moreover, it can be inferred further that teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu, although they vary in educational attainment, do not differ in ways of perceiving emotional intelligence. That is, teachers of HEIs in Sulu perceived in similar ways how individual faculty apply knowledge to different circumstances in life. They do not differ in assessing a group of social, personal, and emotional skills and abilities that affect how a person copes with different clamors and tensions.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable educational attainment has no significant influence on the ways in which teachers of public higher education institutions in Sulu perceive the extent of emotional intelligence. Therefore, the hypothesis that states that "there is no significant difference in the emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu in the context when data are grouped and categorized according to educational attainment" is accepted.

Table 3.6 Differences in the emotional intelligence of teachers in public HEIs in Sulu when data are grouped categorized according to educational attainment

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig .	Description
Perception of emotions	Between	.347	4	.087	.465	.76	Significant
	Within Groups	36.367	19	.186			
	Total	36.714	19				
Managing own emotions	Between	1.434	4	.359	1.559	.18	Not Significant
	Within Groups	44.860	19	.230			
	Total	46.294	19				
Managing other's emotions	Between	1.996	4	.499	2.371	.05	Significant
	Within Groups	41.024	19	.216			
	Total	43.020	19				
Utilization of emotions	Between	.894	4	.224	.738	.56	Not Significant
	Within Groups	59.044	19	.303			
	Total	59.938	19				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

CONCLUSION

This study forwards the conclusions:

- 1) There is sufficient representation of faculty at public HEIs in Sulu in terms of gender, age, civil status, length of service, status of appointment, and educational attainment.
- 2) On average, faculty members of public HEIs in Sulu have an above-average rate of emotional intelligence.
- 3) Generally, teachers of public HEIs in Sulu do not differ in ways of assessing the extent of emotional intelligence.
- 4) This particular study tends to support Lucero and Ocampo, Jr.'s (2019) Model of Emotional Intelligence, which asserts that an individual applies knowledge to different circumstances in life through a group of social, personal, and emotional skills and abilities that affect how a person copes with different clamor and tensions.

IJMERI

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY
EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH AND INNOVATION

Authors retain copyright. Articles published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC-BY) International License. This license allows this work to be copied, distributed, remixed, transformed, and built upon for any purpose provided that appropriate attribution is given, a link is provided to the license, and changes made were indicated.

REFERENCES

- Acain, W. L. (2015). Maximizing Organizational Leadership in Academic Setting. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 15, no. 4, 91-101. <https://doi.org/1694-2493>
- Babbie, E., & Mouton, J. (2001). *The practice of social research*. Cape Town: Oxford University Press.
- Bless, C., & Higson-Smith, C. (1995). *Fundamentals of Social Work Research: A Guide for Students and Beginning Practitioners* (2nd ed.). Juta. <https://doi.org/ISBN 0702134325, 9780702134326>
- Băeșu, C., & Bejinaru, R. (2015). Innovative leadership styles and the influence of emotional intelligence. *The USV Annals of Economics and Public Administration*, 15(3), 136-145.
- Badri-Harun, A., Zainol, M. R., Amzairi, A. M. A. R., & Shaari, Z. H. (2016). Emotional intelligence as mediator between leadership styles and leadership effectiveness: A theoretical framework. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 6(1), 116-121.
- Chatterjee, A., & Kulakli, A. (2015). An empirical investigation of the relationship between emotional intelligence, transactional and transformational leadership styles in banking sector. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 210, 291-300.
- Crowne, K. A., Young, T. M., Goldman, B., Patterson, B., Krouse, A. M., & Proenca, J. (2017). Leading nurses: emotional intelligence and leadership development effectiveness. *Leadership in Health Services*, 30(3), 217-232.
- Dabke, D. (2016). Impact of leader's emotional intelligence and transformational behavior on perceived leadership effectiveness: A multiple source view. *Business Perspectives and Research*, 4(1), 27-40.
- Dartey-Baah, K., & Mekpor, B. (2017). Emotional Intelligence: Does Leadership Style Matter? Employees Perception in Ghana's Banking Sector. *International Journal of Business*, 22(1).
- Doan, T. T. T., Nguyen, L. C. T., & Nguyen, T. D. N. (2020). Emotional intelligence and project success: The roles of transformational leadership and organizational commitment. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(3), 223-233.
- Görgens-Ekermans, G., & Roux, C. (2021). Revisiting The Emotional Intelligence and Transformational Leadership Debate: (How) Does Emotional Intelligence Mater to Effective Leadership? *SA Journal of Human Resource Management/SA Tydskrif vir Menslikehulpbronbestuur*. 19(0), a1279. <https://doi.org/ten.4ten2/sajhrm.v19i0.1279>
- Jovanovica, D., & Ciricb, M. (2016). Benefits of transformational leadership in the context of education. *The European Proceedings of Social & Behavioural Sciences EpSBS*, 497-503.
- Lucero, L. C., & Ocampo Jr, J. M. (2019). Emotional intelligence and leadership trait among master teachers. *Mimbar pendidikan*, 4(1), 55-72.
- Majeed, N., Ramayah, T., Mustamil, N., Nazri, M., & Jamshed, S. (2017). Transformational leadership and organizational citizenship behavior: Modeling emotional intelligence as mediator. *Management & Marketing. Challenges for the Knowledge Society*, 12(4), 571-590.

- Maqbool, R., Sudong, Y., Manzoor, N., & Rashid, Y. (2017). The impact of emotional intelligence, project managers' competencies, and transformational leadership on project success: An empirical perspective. *Project Management Journal*, 48(3), 58-75.
- Obmerga, M. E. (2020). The impact of design thinking and grit on Filipino millennial academic supervisors' transformational leadership attributes: A structural equation model. *Asian Journal on Perspectives in Education*, 1, 24-51.
- Milhem, M., Muda, H., & Ahmed, K. (2019). The effect of perceived transformational leadership style on employee engagement: The mediating effect of leader's emotional intelligence. *Foundations of Management*, 11(1), 33-42.
- Moon, J. (2021). Effect of Emotional Intelligence and Leadership Styles on Risk Intelligent Decision Making and Risk Management. *Journal of Engineering, Project & Production Management*, 11(1).
- Oracion, C. C. (2014). Teacher leadership in public schools in the Philippines (Doctoral dissertation, UCL Institute of Education).
- Schweisfurth, M., Davies, L., Symaco, L. P., & Valiente, O. (2018). Higher education, bridging capital, and developmental leadership in the Philippines: Learning to be a crossover reformer. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 59, 1-8.
- Tyczkowski, B., Vandenhouten, C., Reilly, J., Bansal, G., Kubsch, S. M., & Jakkola, R. (2015). Emotional intelligence (EI) and nursing leadership styles among nurse managers. *Nursing administration quarterly*, 39(2), 172-180.
- Ugoani, J., Amu, C., & Emenike, K. O. (2015). Dimensions of emotional intelligence and transformational leadership: A correlation analysis. *Independent Journal of Management & Production (IJM&P)* v, 6.

IJMERI
INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY
EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH AND INNOVATION

